

Three Types of Non-Perceptuals in *Theaetetus* 185b-186c

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I

The distinction between perception and thought as two different faculties of the mind is one of the most important and lasting contributions of Plato to the history of philosophy. Its origin is to be found in *Theaetetus* 184b-187a¹, where the proper objects for each of faculty are discriminated. While some things, like sounds, colors, and tastes, are considered by the mind through the organs of the senses; there is another type of things that the mind considers autonomously without mediation of those organs. Elements in the second category, like being, are preconditions for several philosophical enterprises, such as getting truth, and, more relevant for the purposes of the dialogue, attaining knowledge. I am going to call the elements in this second category *non-perceptuals*, as they cannot be grasped through perceptual organs.

Since the scholarship attention has been focused in addressing other aspects of the passage, it seems to me that the conception of non-perceptuals that Plato hints in 185b-186c has not yet received complete appreciation. Certainly, previous explorations to the text have revealed certain features of the non-perceptual things, but a more direct reconstruction of the views that are suggested in the passage remains to be undertaken. The objective of this paper is to advance a first attempt to carry out this project, i.e. to provide an elucidation of the views about non-perceptual features that can be extracted from the *Theaetetus* 185b-186c. My main claim is that the mainstream reading of the passage overlooks an important distinction among three different types of non-perceptuals. The argument is advanced as follows. I begin by presenting the discussion carried out in 184b-187a (section II). Then, I put forth two versions of what I call the reductionist assumption, the view that non-perceptuals conforms a unified category (section III). The rejection of the first version of the reductionist assumption (section IV), allows me to introduce and justify the three categories I just mentioned (section V). The objections against the rejection of the second version of the assumption fourth one will provide us with a sketchy characterization of those types and the the way in which they are grasped by the soul (section VI). A summary of the results of this exploration will be last section (VII).

It is important to state three of limits to the scope of this paper from the outset. All that I attempt to here is a preliminary philosophical elucidation of a particularly difficult passage in the *Theaetetus* that improve our understanding of the moral of

¹ Unless otherwise stated, all the translations are from Margaret J. Levett's translation, included in Burnyeat (1990).

the argument. This entail, first, that I will not be concerned with discussing the best translation of the Greek terms used in the passage and other philological concerns. Those matters will be left to the relevant specialists. Second, the best way to cohere the views put forth in the *Theaetetus* with other views held by Plato in other dialogues are far outside from the reach of this paper. In that sense, references to other Platonic works will be kept to minimum. And, third, this paper should be read as an exploratory work. Thus, no detailed theory of non-perceptuals is going to be developed here. But, even in its narrow scope, this seems to be an important task. Understanding the conception of non-perceptuals that Plato insinuates here not only provides us with a better view of his views on perception, thought, and knowledge. Also, if Dorothea Frede is right in her suggestion that the passage under discussion is an interpretative key to understand the dialogue as a whole², the results of this exploration could be important for the understanding of this enigmatic work.

II

In *Theaetetus* 184-187a, Plato puts in Socrates' words the final argument against Theaetetus' proposal that knowledge be defined as sense-perception. The view criticized could be stated as follows: we perceive the world through the senses, this perception generates many sorts of beliefs, some of these beliefs are true, and some of those true beliefs constitute knowledge. (Cf. *Tht.* 151e, 184,b, and 186e). Of course, this view is related to number of claims that Socrates has previously made on the behalf of other philosophers throughout the dialogue, in particular, on behalf of Protagorean relativism (Cf. 166b-168c and 177c-179). I will not address those foreign views in this paper, and my focus will be limited to formulation I have just sketched.

Plato's opposition to the definition of knowledge as perception is carefully constructed in four stages. In Stage 1 (184b-185a), Socrates lays out the background for his objection by getting from Theaetetus the acceptance of two assumptions about perception. First, while asking whether we perceive *with* the bodily organs or *through* the bodily organs, Socrates seeks the acceptance of the implausibility of the idea that perception is an activity *of* the body. On the contrary, perception is an activity of the soul that it exercises *through* body organs (184c-e). This idea is illustrated with the example of the Wooden Horse. Our senses are not like the soldiers in the Trojan horse, that is, many entities trapped in a single body; quite the opposite, all the senses belong to and converge in a single entity, the soul or the mind, that use them as instruments to perceive the perceptible elements in the world. Second, Theaetetus concedes to Socrates that each sense has its proper objects, which are inaccessible to the other senses (184e-185a). That is, sight can

² See, D. Frede (1989) 20-1

perceive colors and hearing perceive sounds, and those are their proper objects; but hearing cannot perceive colors, and eyes cannot access to sounds.

Stage 2 (*Tht.* 185a-e) begins with Socrates' suggestion that there is a thing in common among the all perceptibles: 'they [all] are.' (185a). In other words, sounds, colors, tastes, etc., although are grasped through different organs, they have in common the fact that they have *being*. But being is not the only one feature that perceptibles have in common. All perceptibles also have in common other features such as the fact that one perceptible is different from other things and the same as itself (185a); the fact they have number –i.e., that each of them is one and a couple of them are two (185b)–; and the fact they are similar or dissimilar (185b). But this argument is not limited to perceptual things. In fact, the possession of those features is shared by *everything*, or, to put it conversely, features such as having being and having number are features that all the things has in common. It is natural to call them then "commons." At 185d, Theaetetus makes a list of those common features. Those are: being and not-being, likeness and unlikeness, same and different, one and many, being odd and even, and 'all that is involved with these attributes'. What is crucial from the commons is how the soul grasps them: While Theaetetus can identify a bodily organ capable to grasp certain perceptibles (for example, the taste perceives the saltiness), he is unable to find a bodily power capable to grasp the commons (185d). In the investigation of the common features, he further acknowledges, 'the soul functions through itself' (185e). Thus, the stage ends with the establishment of a crucial distinction: there are some things that the soul 'considers through the bodily powers', whereas there are other things that the soul considers 'alone and through itself' (185e).

After giving some laudatory remarks to Theaetetus as he saved him from a vast amount of talk (*Tht.* 185e), Socrates advances to Stage 3 of his argument (186a-c). In this stage he formulates three sets of questions to Theaetetus. Since those are the crucial elements of this paper, I am going to give a detailed look to them. The *first* set includes two interrogations. To begin, at 186a, Socrates asks whether 'being,' the common 'that accompanies everything,' is a feature that soul grasps through the soul or is a feature grasped through the senses. Theaetetus places being in the first category. Then, he inquiries whether this classification 'also' applies to the others commons such as 'like and unlike, same and different;' and he gets the exact same answer (186a). The *second* group is a singleton. At 186a-b, Socrates asks about the classification of 'the beautiful and ugly, good and bad.' Theaetetus places those elements in the same category, but he adds an important qualification: 'above all, I think that the soul examines the being they have as compared one to another. Here it seems to make a calculation within itself of past and present in relation to the future' (186b). At this moment, Socrates stops dramatically the flow of the discussion –he says, 'not so fast,' – and he introduces the *third* set of elliptical,

interrogative remarks. He asks: ‘Wouldn’t you say that is through touch that one perceives the hardness of what is hard, and similarly the softness of what is soft?’ (186b). After obtaining Theaetetus’ agreement, he is now who introduces a clarification to the claim: ‘But regarding to their being –the fact they are- their opposition to one another, and the being, again, of this opposition, the matter is different. Here the soul itself attempts to reach a decision by rising to compare them with one another’ (186b). Furthermore, Socrates concludes the stage 3 with an additional clarification about who to grasp the being of hardness and softness. While certain things can be perceived naturally by humans and animals since their birth; there are other things which require ‘calculations regarding their being and their advantageous come, when they do, only as a result of a long and arduous development, involving a good deal of trouble and education’ (186c). As I understand it, this remark is meant to be applied only to the things in sets of questions. This reading will be justified below.³

Finally, in Stage 4 (*Tht.* 186c-187a), Socrates uses the former distinction to provide the final case against Theaetetus’ definition of knowledge. His reasoning, one of clearest in the dialogue, is the following: Given that attaining being is a precondition of attaining truth, and truth is a precondition for attaining knowledge (186c), hence, knowledge cannot be found in the experiences; instead, it should be found in the process of reasoning about those experiences, which is the way in which the soul access to truth and being (186d). Socrates continues getting Theaetetus to accept that the distinctions that they have agreed undermine his definition of knowledge as perception. The definitive conclusion of this argument is that knowledge should no be found in the faculty of sense perception, but ‘in the activity of the soul when it is busy by itself about the things which are’ (187a). Now Theaetetus proposal is successfully refuted: Perception cannot be identified not knowledge.

III

Despite the great interest that this passage has attracted,⁴ the scholarship has almost neglected the discussion Plato’s views about the non-perceptibles. Contemporary discussions of the passage has been mainly focused in three issues:

³ Section VI.

⁴ The contemporary discussion of this passage initiated with John M. Cooper’s seminal paper (1970), which challenged the classical readings of the passage advocated by Francis M. Cornford; (1935) 102–9 After the publication of this paper, it is not only a small exaggeration to say that most of the academic discussion has been occupied with developing or rejecting Cooper’s views. The most important works on this passage are: Holland (1973); McDowell (1973) 185–193; Burnyeat (1976); Modrak (1981); Shea (1985); M. Frede (1987); Bostock (1988) 110–145; Fine (1988); Burnyeat (1990) 52–60; Silverman (1990); Bobonich (2002) 295–331; Sedley (2004) 105–114; Chappell (2004) 141–150; Lorenz (2006) 74–95; Loot (2011)

(i) providing an account of Plato's theory notion of perception, (ii) determining the notion of belief (*doxa*) that is implied in the argument, and, (iii) explaining the notion being and process of the soul to grasp it. Regarding (i) and (ii), existing interpretations fall in two groups. On the one hand, a majoritarian view which claims that perception and thought are two different activities of the soul, one realized through the senses, and one done when the soul considers things by itself.⁵ In that regard, given that perception cannot access non-perceptuals, and non-perceptuals are required for the formation of beliefs, then, perception cannot form even the simplest beliefs. On the other hand, a minority of scholars holds that Plato could not have meant such a strong view that grasping non-perceptuals is required for every belief. They argue that perception can at least yield simple beliefs about the objects that are perceived. In that regard, the contrast in *Tht.* 185e is not between two different activities of the soul, perception and thought, but a contrast between two models of thought: a model that occurs when the soul considers things through bodily powers which yields to simple, perceptual beliefs, and a different model that occurs in the soul's autonomous considerations of the non-perceptuals, which gives rise to a different set of more complex beliefs.⁶ Both interpretations bear a strong relationship to the issues discussed in (iii). The debate here is whether being, one of the non-perceptuals, should be interpreted as a 'copula' or as 'existence.'⁷ Being-as-copula can be exemplified with 'x is F', where 'being' is the copula between the noun x and the property or quality F, such as in 'Theaetetus is smart.' Being-as-existence can be presented as 'x is' (Theaetetus is), where x having being should be read as x's existence, x's essence, or x's objectivity. Normally, supporters of the first, majoritarian reading of (i)-(ii) accept a reading of the being-as-copula formulation, while supporters of the second reading commit to being-as-existence as ground for his claim.⁸

This led us to our main concern. While being occupied on other issues⁹, most of the participants of the debate seem to rely on the idea that the passage provides one

⁵ See, Burnyeat 'Plato and the Grammar of Perceiving'. Others defended of this account includes Fine (1988); Shea (1985); M. Frede (1987); Silverman (1990) Recently, this perspective received support from Lorenz (2006) 74–95; and, Bobonich (2002)

⁶ This view initiated with Cooper's influential paper (1970) and it was accepted by Deborah Modrak (See, (1981)) Recently, a similar reading it has been defended by Gerson (2003) 204–213

⁷ For this distinction, see Kahn (2009) 1–2

⁸ Notably, Tomas Loot recently suggested an interpretation that endorses a view that perception cannot form beliefs (that is, the majoritarian reading), while rejecting the 'copula' account of being. See, Loot (2011)

⁹ Each interpretation has to meet certain interpretative challenges. For example, they have to provide an account that overcomes some incoherencies between the uses of some words in stages 1-2 of the passage compared to stages 3-4, and, they must include an account of perception and

single type the non-perceptuals, or, at least, the all non-perceptuals are reducible to a single account. I will call this idea the *reductionist assumption*.

To appreciate better the role of such assumption in the argument, it is helpful to distinguish between two versions of it. The first version takes all non-perceptuals as reducible to one single category. Consider for instance the classic reading advanced by Francis M. Cornford who understood the totality of things that the soul grasps without mediation of senses as Forms¹⁰. The interesting element here is not the idea of Form, but the fact that he unifies of the non-perceptuals in a single type. More contemporary scholarship, yet it rejects Cornford's Formist reading¹¹, still continues to accept the first version of the reductionist assumption. For example, John McDowell, David Bostock, and Deborah Modrak explicitly say that three sets of question that Socrates puts forth in Stage 3 (*Tht.* 186a-c) merely 'add up' new elements to the list of commons previously enumerated by Theaetetus in Stage 2 (185d)¹². Clearly, the suggestion seems to be that all non-perceptuals are commons, and then, Plato accepts a single type of non-perceptual whose exhaustive list is completed by both by Socrates and Theaetetus in the successive steps at Stages 2 and 3.

The second version of the assumption is more nuanced. This reading may recognize a variety of different types of non-perceptuals, but it gives explanatory priority to 'being' above all the others.¹³ There are two important textual elements that support this reading. One the one hand, the nature of the being is exclusively discussed in some passages (e.g., 185b and 186a), which seems to give the sensation that this non-perceptual some sort special role. On the other hand, and more importantly, the object that seems to be grasped all the non-perceptuals it is being. Notice that in the second and third questions of the Stage 3, what is grasped is 'the being' of the beautiful-ugly, good-bad, and, hardness-softness. Then, since the explanation of the process of grasping non-perceptuals is reducible to an explanation of grasping being; being cannot be put as one more of the many non-perceptuals. Being is, for the second version, the master non-perceptual that allows us to grasp the others.

To summate, while the first version is the suggestion that all non-perceptuals are commons; the suggestion in the second reading is that process of grasping the non-perceptual or explainable in reference to one master non-perceptual. In other

belief that coheres with previous Platonic works (mainly, *The Republic*) or justify a change in Plato's views on those matters (mainly, in *The Sophist*).

¹⁰ Cornford (1935) 102–109, especially 106.

¹¹ I think that Cornford's interpretation was decisively refuted by Cooper (1970) 127–8, 137–9

¹² See, McDowell (1973) 191–2; Bostock (1988) 122, and, Modrak (1981) 37

¹³ Loot (2011) 356.

words, the former holds that non-perceptuals are one type of thing; the latter suggests that they may be different things, but the process to grasp them is a single one.

IV

It is my view that this reductionist assumption does not make justice to the complexity of this passage. I will begin by rejecting the claim that all the non-perceptual are commons advanced by first version of the assumption, and then I proceed to justify three types of non-perceptuals that I find in the passage.

The point of departure of my rejection of the first version is the explicit list of commons introduced by Theaetetus at 186d, which are labeled in 185e as ‘the common features of everything.’ That list includes being-not being, likeness and difference, same and different, one and many, which were not discussed in 185a-d. Two facts are noticeable. First, Theaetetus makes sure to include one ‘obvious’ common that was left (odd and even) in the second sentence of the list. This give us reason to think that the list is restrictive. Second, this interpretation gains weight when we consider that Socrates accepts the restrictive character of the list with a very clear language: ‘You follow me exceedingly well. *These are just* the things I am asking about’. It seems to be clear, then, that the commons are those listed in 185d, and not others,

There are a couple of important conceptual reasons that gives further support to this reading. The ‘common features of everything’ listed in 185d are, in my concept, the same things ‘accompanies everything’ that Socrates suggested in 186a. Here, we have to be careful. When Socrates asks for second time to Theaetetus whether he would classify being as perceptual or a non-perceptual, the philosopher explains that being is, ‘above all, something that accompanies everything’ (186a). But it seems to be appropriate to extend this qualification to the all the commons listed in 185d. Notice that after obtaining from Theaetetus that being is non-perceptual, he introduces a new question: ‘*Also* like and unlike, same and different?’ To that, Theaetetus answers unqualifiedly ‘yes’. We should take the *also* in this question as meaning that the same features of the question for the ‘being’ applies similarly to ‘like’ and ‘unlike’, and ‘same’ and ‘different’. If this is correct, it seems just natural to extend this rationale to all the other commons because, after all, they also are things that accompany everything. This interpretation is strengthened when we take into account that Theaetetus answer has no further qualifications –unlike in the following two questions in 186b. Therefore, the commons in 184d are the same are things that ‘accompanies everything’ of 185e.

Being a feature that ‘accompanies everything’ is a really important characteristic of the commons. The implication seems to be that it is not conceptually possible for a thing *not* to have one of those features; or, to put it differently; all conceptually

conceivable objects have, by necessity, each one of the commons. Notice that all conceptually conceivable things have being with regard to themselves (i.e., they are what they are), and, at the same time, they have do not have being of what they are not (i.e., they are not what they are not). Similarly happens with the other commons: they are similar to things of the same kind, but different from others; and so on. On the contrary, the other types of non-perceptuals that are mentioned in the two further questions of Stage 3 deserve different consideration. If we focus, for example, in the features of hardness and softness stated in 185b, it seems to be clear that not everything that exists have hardness or softness *stricto sensu*. If we consider perceptibles, it does not seem to be fully accurate to say that sound or a color is ‘hard’ or ‘soft’; it seems to be better description of a to say that a sound is loud or quiet, and that a color is bright or dark. If we think in objects that cannot be grasped through perception, their lacking of hardness and softness is more perspicuous. Clearly, objects such as thoughts, numbers, and geometrical figures cannot plausibly be thought as having hardness or softness. If this is correct, it seems to be implausible that everything have hardness or softness, and it seems even less plausible to think that the being of hardness and softness is a feature common to all things. For what it is important now, then, we have established a first distinction: the features discussed between features pointed in the third question of Stage 3 (hardness-softness) cannot be regarded as ‘commons’, not only because they not includes in the list in 182b, but also, more importantly, because they are not things that accompany everything.

This interpretation requires, however, a different explanation for the second question of stage 3 concerning to beauty-ugliness and good-bad. Unlike hardness and softness, it seems plausible to think that everything is either beautiful or ugly, or either is good or bad. This is strengthened if we take into account Greek’s views of beauty and goodness; it is a common idea of Ancient Philosophy there is some sort of beauty and goodness even in abstract objects, human behaviours, attitudes, thoughts, etc.¹⁴ This seems to lead us to think that they should be considered among the commons. The natural question is, then, why did Plato consider those in a different place instead of placing them in the same list of *Tht.* 186d? The reasons for that, I think, is related to the way in which those features are grasped. This is the most important reason to differentiate between the commons and other non-perceptibles. The process grasping of the commons seems much simpler than the process of grasping beauty-ugly and goodness-badness, where the soul needs to make a ‘calculation within itself of past and present in relation to future’. Hence, it may be true that the features of the second question as possessed by everything, but that does not transform them in commons; the process for grasping them is

¹⁴ See our discussion about beauty in section VI.

much complex than the process of grasping the features listed in 185d. It is clear, then, that not all the non-perceptuals are commons.

V

By rejecting the first reading of the reductionist assumption, we are now in a better position to appreciate a distinction that was subtly introduced in Theaetetus 185b-186c. Instead of being one single type of non-perceptuals, there are three categories of them. We can only appreciate this distinction when we are active readers as Plato requires from us, that is, when we take note of the form and structure of the argument, when we are alert in detecting verbal standpoints and sub-textual evidence, and we when complete the argument by our own consideration.

The justification of this distinction begins with a closer look to the three sets of questions in stage 3. At this moment, Socrates and Theaetetus already agree on the distinction between perceptuals and non-perceptuals. What Plato does in each of the sets of elliptical questions is developing a new category of non-perceptuals.

The *first* set, at *Th.* 186a -where Socrates asks about being, like-unlike, same-different- is merely a repetition of the commons that were listed in 185b. What is crucial to stress here is the relationship between the two questions that is expressed by the word 'also' that connects them. As I have argued above¹⁵, the qualification that Socrates introduces for being in 186b, i.e., that is a thing that 'accompanies everything', applies as well to the features mentioned in the second question. Hence, it is plausible to think that this applies also to all the commons listed in 185b. Here we have the first type of non-perceptuals: the *commons*, the features that apply to everything. A very important point to notice is that there is no indication on how the commons are to be grasped. Once again, unlike to second and third set of questions, the first set ends without further qualifications. If the principle *ubi Plato non distinguit, nec nos distinguere debemus* is wise principle to apply here,¹⁶ then we have reason to think that the commons are grasped directly by the soul. That is, if the Plato has not pointed a special mental process to grasp the commons, we must assume that they are grasped in the simplest way possible.

The *second* set is conformed by a single elliptical question and its answer (186b). The question concerning to beautiful-ugly, and good-bad is introduced with the words 'what about.' What Plato means by this is that there is not continuity between the first set and of the second; that is, the features that apply to the second set does not apply to the first one. The most relevant part of the passage is 'Theaetetus'

¹⁵ See, above, section IV.

¹⁶ Here, I am paraphrasing the principle for legal interpretation contained in *Digesta* 6,2,8: *ubi lex non distinguit, nec nos distinguere debemus*.

answer. Here, he begins to qualify the second set claiming that the being of those features is grasped by ‘compar[ing] with one another’. One may argue that this opposition seems to connect the second set with the commons because. Recall that also in grasping the being of the commons, the understanding of some opposition. For example, there is an opposition between being and not-being, and similar and dissimilar. As this second set also include opposition, this seems to be a reason to connect them with commons. This does not seem to me a decisive element that justifies that the second set should be included among the commons. As we will explain in moment¹⁷, the grasping of some opposition is needed among all the non-perceptibles. More importantly, accepting the unity between the second set and commons will overlook the crucial element is second sentence of the qualification, where Theaetetus explains the particular way in which this second type of non-perceptibles are grasped: For grasping beauty-ugliness and good-bad, the soul ‘*seems to be making a calculation within itself of past and present in relation to future*’ (*Tht.* 186b). In other words, the crucial step in considering the features listed in the second question is not through considering the ‘opposition’ in them; but, instead, through considering their being in a particular way: through a calculation in time. As the most important element relevant is a temporal calculation, it seems appropriate to dub this second group as *temporal* things.

Finally, the introduction of the *third* and last set of questions (186b-c) is a slightly more abrupt. With the expression ‘*eche dé,*’ which is translated at ‘not so fast, now’ (Levet) or ‘hold on’ (McDowell), Socrates elliptically asks Theaetetus about considering the hardness and softness of things. I agree with McDowell that his express is introduced to indicate to Theaetetus that he is danger of missing an important point¹⁸. Let us examine carefully the passage. At the beginning, by stating the soul perceives hardness and softness by mediation of the bodily organs, Socrates reinforces the previous point that the soul consider perceptuals through senses. The point here is not to restate a previously introduced distinction. It is important to notice that the particular perceptuals has been meticulously chosen: Socrates does not pick out perceptuals which lack of opposites, such as a color (yellow) or a sound (the note ‘A#’); he selects a perceptual that has a clear opposite, i.e. the hardness or softness of a material object. Let us call the latter oppositional perceptuals. The crucial point of the passage is to be found in the second question. Here, when Socrates clarifies that the consideration of the *being* of the oppositional perceptuals can only be grasped by the soul, explains very carefully that the process to grasp the being: ‘*Here the soul itself attempts to reach a decision by rising to compare them with one another*’. (*Tht.* 186b). What I understand here, is that Socrates distinguishes between (a) the being of the oppositional perceptual itself and (b) the being of the opposition of

¹⁷ See, Section VI.

¹⁸ McDowell (1973) 109

that is derived from this perceptual, which is a non-perceptual thing. While (a) is a normal common, (b) is a different type of non-perceptual at the intersection between perceptuals and non-perceptuals¹⁹.

The most important thing now is that we have found a third category of non-perceptual different from the commons and the *temporal* things: while the former are grasped directly and the later grasped in calculation of the part and future, this third group by an oppositional calculus. Moreover, the first two categories are non-perceptuals *simpliciter*, this third category contains elements of a very particular sort: they are non-perceptual derived from a special type of perceptual, i.e., oppositional perceptual. Therefore, it is completely clear that the first reading was a completely mistaken assumption. Instead of being one single category of non-perceptuals, there are three types instead: The *common* things, the *temporal*, and, the being of *oppositional things*.

VI

Now, let us turn our attention now to the second reading of the reductionist assumption. Despite its complexity and the textual evidence for it, I think this second reading is not convincing for two reasons that could be explained succinctly. The first reason is very simple. When Theaetetus collects his lists of commons at *Tht.* 185d, he positions ‘being’ in the same level as ‘like and unlike’ and ‘one and many,’ and the others. Also, as I have already noticed, Socrates accepts this list very happily by clarifying that those, and not others, are the commons that interest him. It seems to be clear, then, that no special place is given to being by Theaetetus or Socrates. Relatedly, the fact that there are some questions concerned exclusively to being, it is easily explained by the very structure of the argument: Plato uses successive questions to introduce new elements in his argument. In the case of being, this is just apparent both in the succession of questions before 185d -where Socrates inquires first about being (185a-c), and then about like and unlike and other commons (185b)-, and the successions of questions after the lists, whose nuances were explained in sections IV and V of this paper.

The second reason is much more complex and important. The fact that being is mentioned in all the questions in Stage 3 does not count as decisive evidence for the second version. Since Being is a common, and, as such, it is a feature that everything has; it is only a platitude to point that the oppositional and calculational things have being. What it is really important to notice is Plato stresses on the idea that there are many important differences in the way we grasp being as common, or being *simpliciter*, from the way we grasp the being of the temporal and oppositional non-perceptuals. In other words, Plato’s characterization of being *simpliciter* is much

¹⁹ I will return to his matter in section VI.

different from his characterisation of the being of non-oppositional. What is are exactly three different ways to the being of non-perceptuals? We already know that commons are grasped directly, a temporal things require a temporal calculus, and oppositional things requires an oppositional calculus. Let me provide a general overview of these three different processes of the soul.

First off, the way in which the being simpliciter is grasped is very straightforward. We already have pointed that there is no explanation of how commons are grasped. The suggestion seems to be that being *simpliciter* and the other commons are grasped directly, that is, only by thinking about the object, without any type of temporal or oppositional calculation, we grasp the respective non-perceptual.

Second, let us move now to account the *temporal* things, a more interesting group that include beauty-ugliness and good-bad. The natural question seems to be: how a can a feature be grasped to a calculation of past and future? To explain this enigmatic calculus, I am going to set aside the account of goodness and basses²⁰, and I will concentrate in beauty-ugliness. More particularly, I will give a closer look to the passage where Socrates praises Theaetetus (185e). The relevant statement is the following, according to Mrs. Levett's translation: 'Yes, Theaetetus, you would say that, because you are handsome and not ugly as Theodorus would have it. For handsome is as handsome says.' Unfortunately, Levett's translation does not allow us to appreciate of the passage for two aspects²¹. First, the word translated in the first sentence as 'handsome' is the Greek word *kalos*, which is commonly translated as beautiful. This modification conceals the previous appearances of the word in the dialogue.²² Second, there seems to be a small mistranslation in the second sentence. Mrs. Levett uses the say word for Theaetetus and his speech (handsome), while the word used to characterise the speech is the adverb *kalós*, not the adjective *kalos*. So it seems to be better translated as 'he 'speaks handsomely' (*ho kalós legon*). With those remarks in mind, it seems to me that a more accurate translation of the passage following: 'Yes, Theaetetus, you would say that because you are beautiful (*kalos*) and not ugly (*aischros*), as Theodorus was saying. For someone who speaks beautifully (*ho kalós legon*) is beautiful (*kalos*) and good (*agathos*)'.

²⁰ I am going to explain by focusing in beauty and ugliness. The reason to exclude goodness from the current discussion is derived from the very special role they play role in the dialogue. It seems to be that the calculation being of the good is introduced with the intention to refute some views that Socrates puts forward on behalf of Protagoras in 142, 166-8 and 177-9. Since a proper discussion of the notions of goodness and badness would require explaining with its proper object, I cannot make justice to the richness of this notion here.

²¹ See, Boeri (2006) 61, n.7 and 182, n. 201

²² As we will see in a moment, the word was previously translated as beautiful at *Tht.* 142 and 143.

Now, when those terms are clarified what we see find here an clear example of the calculation used by the soul to grasp the *temporal* being. Recall the beginning of the dialogue between Socrates and Theaetetus. At 144e, Theodorus, Theaetetus' master, when he was introducing his pupil to the philosopher, he said that the young mathematician was not *kalos* (beautiful, in Mrs. Levett's translation). This seems to be an accurate description of his physical appearance, as Theaetetus has certain resemblances to Socrates. (see, *Tht.* 144e). However, after making a 'calculation' or 'consideration' of Theaetetus' being, this ended not being truth (see, 145b, 148e, 151c): Socrates found that, contrary the appearances, that Theaetetus was in fact beautiful. The most important thing to notice here is that Socrates' soul grasps the being of Theaetetus' in the same way he explains at 186b. That is, Theaetetus' beauty is grasped through a calculation of the past and present in relation to future. The past and present here are the remarks about Theaetetus' appearance made by Theodorus. The future here is related to the kind of person that Theaetetus will become. To see it, we should recall that Socrates told Euclides, one of the characters of the background dialogue, that Theaetetus, a person with an impressive natural ability, will become an individual from whom 'we should inevitably hear more' in the future (146c-d). Socrates judgement, as the good prophet he was, ended up being correct. By the time of Theaetetus' death, he has deemed to be *kalos* and *agathos* by everybody (142b).

For reasons of space and time, I am not going to discuss here the third topic and the comments about the value of my objections (one additional page excluded).

VII

Now, it is time to conclude. In that paper, I have defended an interpretation of Socrates' final refutation of the argument of Theaetetus' definition of knowledge as perception, which I expect, brings to the light an important element: the distinction between three types of things: the *commons* the *temporal* things, and the *oppositional* things. Now, we are in a position to see that perception cannot be knowledge because it cannot attain commons, it cannot calculate, and it cannot understand opposition. Only thought can do that. Those are, I think, important elements to complete our account of Plato's theories of thought and perception. Yet provisional, the former results seem to be interesting way to explore these notions in the future.

References

- Bobonich, C. (2002) *Plato's Utopia Recast: His Later Ethics and Politics* (Oxford)
- Boeri, M. (2006) *Platón: Teeteto*, tr. M. Boeri (Buenos Aires)

- Bostock, D. (1988) *Plato's Theaetetus* (Oxford)
- Burnyeat, M.F. (1976) 'Plato on the Grammar of Perceiving', *The Classical Quarterly* 26, 29–51
- (1990) *The Theaetetus Of Plato*, tr. M.J. Levett (Indianapolis - Cambridge)
- Chappell, T. (2004) *Reading Plato's Theaetetus* (Indianapolis - Cambridge)
- Cooper, J.M. (1970) 'Plato on Sense-Perception and Knowledge ("Theaetetus" 184-186)', *Phronesis* 15, 123–46
- Cornford, F.M. (1935) *Plato's Theory of Knowledge: the Theaetetus and the Sophist* (London)
- Fine, G. (1988) 'Plato on Perception: A reply to Professor Turnbull "Becoming and Intelligibility"', in J. Annas and R.H. Grimm (eds), *Oxford Studies in Ancient Philosophy: Supplementary Volume: 1988* (Oxford)
- Frede, D. (1989) 'The Soul's Silent Dialogue: A Non-aporetic Reading of the Theaetetus', *Proceedings of the Cambridge Philological Society* 215, 20–49
- Frede, M. (1987) 'Observations on perception in Plato's later dialogues', in *Essays in Ancient Philosophy* (Minneapolis) 3–10
- Gerson, L.P. (2003) *Knowing Persons: A Study in Plato* (Oxford)
- Holland, A.J. (1973) 'An argument in Plato's "Theaetetus" 184-6', *Philosophical Quarterly* 23, 97–114
- Kahn, C.H. (2009) *Essays on Being*
- Loot, T. (2011) 'Plato on the Rationality of Belief. Theaetetus 184-7', *Trames A Journal of the Humanities and Social Sciences* 11(65/66), 339–64
- Lorenz, H. (2006) *The Brute Within: Appetitive Desire in Plato and Aristotle* (Oxford)
- McDowell, J. (1973) *Plato: Theaetetus (translation with notes)* (Oxford)
- Modrak, D.K.W. (1981) 'Perception and Judgment in the Theaetetus', *Phronesis: A journal for Ancient Philosophy* 26, 35–54
- Sedley, D.N. (2004) *The Midwife of Platonism: Text And Subtext in Plato's Theaetetus* (Oxford)
- Shea, J. (1985) 'Judgment and Perception in Theaetetus 184-186', *Journal of the History of Philosophy* 23, 1–14

Silverman, A. (1990) 'Plato on Perception and "Commons"', *The Classical Quarterly* 40, 148–85